

Modelling infrastructure long-term planning and resilience – a NISMOD tools literature review

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Introduction

NISMOD (National Infrastructure Systems Model) is a suite of Python-based tools and libraries designed for analysing and modelling infrastructure systems. Developed since 2010 through successive research projects it enables strategic planning and resilience assessment for infrastructure networks. NISMOD provides tools, frameworks, and packages to model and analyse infrastructure systems, focusing on long-term strategic planning, sustainable development, and resilience assessment. Researchers, policymakers, governments, and private sector organizations use NISMOD to support data-driven infrastructure planning and decision-making. A vast volume of analysis and peer-reviewed papers, project reports, conference abstracts and posters on novel spatial models of infrastructure networks, impact assessment, risk and resilience analysis for interconnected systems have been produced through NISMOD suite of tools. smif¹, OpenGIRA², snkit³, snail⁴ are the main tools of the suite, together with the starter data-kits⁵ and Global Resilience Index (GRI) Risk Viewer⁶ to support climate adaptation decision-making by identifying spatial vulnerabilities and risks under current and future climate scenarios.

NISMOD (Hall et al., 2016)⁷ was developed by the Infrastructure Transitions Research Consortium (ITRC)⁸, to include a prototype integrated national-scale infrastructure database (NISMOD-DB), a modelling software of the long-term capacity/demand requirements of infrastructure (NISMOD-LP) and a modelling software of interdependent infrastructure systems risk and vulnerability (NISMOD-RV). NISMOD-DB was able to represent the spatial (geographic/location)

¹ <https://github.com/nismod/smif>

² <https://github.com/nismod/open-gira>

³ <https://github.com/nismod/snkit>

⁴ <https://github.com/nismod/snail>

⁵ <https://github.com/nismod/irv-datapkg/blob/main/records.csv>

⁶ <https://global.infrastructureresilience.org/>

⁷ Hall, J. W. (Ed.). (2016). The future of national infrastructure. Cambridge University Press.

⁸ <https://www.itrc.org.uk/index.html>

characteristics of infrastructure systems as well as their non-spatial properties (Barr et al., 2013)⁹.

The “Strategic analysis of the future of national infrastructure” (Hall et al., 2017)¹⁰ describes how NISMOD was developed, setting out a methodology for long-term analysis of the performance of national infrastructure systems. It included each infrastructure sector - energy, transport, digital communications, water supply, wastewater, flood protection and solid waste - in a consistent framework with assessed interdependencies between sectors. This is shown in Figure 1¹¹. The methodology, then applied for other countries as reproducible in all its parts, expanded to become a collection of tools to do infrastructure risk and resilience analysis and policy support and was supported with the world’s first infrastructure ‘system-of-systems’ model, developed for long-term decision analysis in interdependent infrastructure systems.

Figure 1: Scheme of the use of NISMOD for national infrastructure assessment (<https://www.itrc.org.uk/using-system-of-systems-modelling-and-simulation-to-inform-sustainable-infrastructure-choices/>)

⁹ Barr, S., Alderston, D., Robson, C., Otto, A., Hall, J., Thacker, S., & Pant, R. (2013). A national scale infrastructure database and modelling environment for the UK.

¹⁰ Hall, J. W., Thacker, S., Ives, M. C., Cao, Y., Chaudry, M., Blainey, S. P., & Oughton, E. J. (2017, February). Strategic analysis of the future of national infrastructure. In *Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers-Civil Engineering* (Vol. 170, No. 1, pp. 39-47). Thomas Telford Ltd.

¹¹ <https://www.itrc.org.uk/using-system-of-systems-modelling-and-simulation-to-inform-sustainable-infrastructure-choices/>

NISMOD open-source code and open data

smif (Simulation Modelling Integration Framework, Russell et al. 2020¹², Usher and Russell 2019¹³) is a framework to support the creation, management and running of system-of-systems models. It helps handling collections of system simulation models interconnected through dependencies on data produced by each other. It permits to add simulation models to the system, connecting inputs and outputs thanks to a library of data adapters or user-defined more specific ones, to perform common data conversion. It allows also to create a library of models, with multi-dimensional input, outputs, parameters and metadata to feed a simulation model wrapper that uses smif. Additionally, the tool repository includes a discussion on when and why it may be useful, along with clear instructions for installation and usage, all fully open source.

OpenGIRA (Open Global Infrastructure Risk/Resilience Analysis, Thomas et al. 2025¹⁴) is a Snakemake¹⁵ workflow that provides an automated pipeline for reproducible analysis anywhere in the world to produce maps per-country and of larger areas, charts/stats of exposure per admin region, per hazard type, scenario, epoch. Infrastructures considered are transport, electricity, water, communications systems, subject to hazards like river flooding, storm surge coastal flooding, tropical cyclones. Thanks to this open-source python tool it is possible for the user to estimate direct and indirect damages to physical networks and people and the economy.

snkit (Russell et al. 2023¹⁶), a spatial networks toolkit, helps putting order and make sense of spatial network data, with the possibility of adding endpoints to edges in networks, split edges at connecting points, create nodes and edges ids, from and to ids creating correspondences between edges and nodes layers. The tool is cited in Gaboardi et al. (2021)¹⁷ as the most comparable python functionality to spaghetti and by Fleischmann et al. (2026)¹⁸ as an open-source methods for street network analysis.

¹² Tom Russell, Will Usher, Roald Lemmen, Thibault Lestang, Fergus Cooper, Craig Robson, & Rose Dickinson. (2020). nismod/smif: v1.3.2 (v1.3.2.post2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4327006>

¹³ Will Usher and Tom Russell. (2019) A Software Framework for the Integration of Infrastructure Simulation Models. *Journal of Open Research Software*, 7: 16 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5334/jors.265>

¹⁴ Fred Thomas, Tom Russell, Thibault Lestang, Max Robertson, & Alberto Fernandez-Perez. (2025). nismod/open-gira: v0.4.1 (v0.4.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17990977>

¹⁵ <https://snakemake.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

¹⁶ Tom Russell, Aman Majid, Fred Thomas, Elco Koks, & Julien Montant. (2023). tomalrussell/snkit: v1.9.0 (v1.9.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3379650>

¹⁷ Gaboardi, J., Rey, S., & Lumnitz, S. (2021). spaghetti: spatial network analysis in PySAL. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 6(62).

¹⁸ Fleischmann, M., Vybornova, A., Gaboardi, J. D., Brázdová, A., & Dančejová, D. (2026). Adaptive continuity-preserving simplification of street networks. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 123, 102354.

snail (Russell et al. 2024¹⁹) is a Python package designed to support the analysis of potential impacts from climate hazards and other threats on infrastructure networks. It enables the intersection of infrastructure vector layers (points, lines, polygons) with hazard raster layers, typically return-period maps provided in raster format. The package can split features according to a grid defined by its affine transform, width, and height, including grids derived from a GeoTIFF file, and attach the values from each raster band to the resulting split features as new attributes. It also supports the transformation of grid indices (i, j), representing column and row positions in a rectangular grid, into geographic coordinates (x, y) within the coordinate reference system (CRS) of the input and output files.

Starter Data Kits (Infrastructure Resilience Assessment Data Packages, Russell et al. 2025²⁰) are open-source collections of data at the national level extracted from different global datasets that constitute the base data useful to carry out climate risk and resilience analysis of infrastructure systems. 249 between countries and sub-countries, covering the whole world, are available now, updated in July 2025. The process of extraction is available on GitHub (<https://github.com/nismod/irv-datapkg/tree/main>) for anyone to be able to reproduce the download for the most updated version of data.

The **Global Resilience Index (GRI) Risk Viewer** (Russell et al, 2025²¹) is a data and analytics platform that provides global insights into hazards, exposure, vulnerability, and risk affecting infrastructure and populations worldwide. The tool is designed to support climate adaptation decision-making by identifying spatial patterns of vulnerability and risk under both current and future climate scenarios. GRI follows the development of a in “*Decision support systems for resilient strategic transport networks in low-income countries*” (Hickford et al. 2023)²², which presented the first multi-state transport infrastructure decision support system developed for a low-income country context, covering Uganda, Zambia, Kenya, and Tanzania. The online platform²³ aimed to support climate-resilient investment planning for strategic road and rail networks by integrating future development scenarios, climate risk and flooding assessments, network criticality and vulnerability analysis, and sustainability indicators, with strong stakeholder engagement guiding its design and application.

¹⁹ Russell, T., Lestang, T., Schlosser, I., Fuldauer, L., Pant, R., & Horvát, S. (2024). snail: spatial networks impact assessment library (v0.5.4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14507011>

²⁰ Tom Russell, Diana J. Jaramillo, & Fred Thomas. (2025). nismod/irv-datapkg: v0.2.1 (v0.2.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16678519>

²¹ Tom Russell, Maciej Ziarkowski, Fred Thomas, Roald Lemmen, Chris Nicholas, Raghav Pant, Alexander Shiarella, Jihyeon Jeong, & Gordon Glasgow. (2025). nismod/infra-risk-vis: v0.4.4 (v0.4.4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15011304>

²² Hickford, A. J., Blainey, S. P., Pant, R., Jaramillo, D., Russell, T., Preston, J., Hall, J. W., Young, M. and Glasgow, G. (2023). Decision Support Systems for Resilient Strategic Transport Networks in Low-Income Countries: Final Report. High Volume Transport Applied Research Programme. Doi: <https://transport-links.com/download/final-report-decision-support-systems-for-resilient-strategic-transport-networks-in-low-income-countries/>

²³ <https://east-africa.infrastructureresilience.org/>

Review

A large body of literature covers the NISMOD toolkit's components and their application to infrastructure network analysis and resilience assessment. Peer reviewed academic journals, conference proceedings, reports and book chapters and the analysis made through the tools are summarized and reported in the next sections.

Of the 26 sources cited in this literature review, spanning peer-reviewed journals, conference proceedings, book chapters, and technical reports, only four are not open-access. Furthermore, all processing code and methodologies are publicly available on GitHub, enabling free application of the NISMOD tools and ensuring full reproducibility of the analysis across any infrastructure-hazard-scenario combination.

Academic journals

smif (simulation model integration framework)²⁴ is described by Usher and Russell (2019)²⁵ in "A Software Framework for the Integration of Infrastructure Simulation Models ". Both the paper and tool are open source, explaining and allowing the reproducibility of the process, its parameterisations, and the possibility of testing alternative approaches to long-term decision-making and planning across the connected models.

NISMOD was first applied to the UK and its sub-regions and catchments, for different infrastructure systems, scenarios and hazards.

Pant et al. (2016)²⁶ developed and demonstrated a NISMOD methodology informing better systems analysis for railway networks in Great Britain, applying it to critical infrastructure and vulnerability assessment and reproducible elsewhere. A networks approach was applied to modelling interdependent critical infrastructures and building a vulnerability assessment framework, providing a detailed procedure to build topological interdependent networks based on physical, spatial and functional characteristics. The model allows flow estimation and disruption, and consequent loss, through all possible interdependencies between assets.

Pant et al. (2018)²⁷ also utilised NISMOD in an integrated framework for critical infrastructure flood impact assessment, together with the mathematical structure at the base of it, and applied it to the Thames catchment. They assembled a multi-modal infrastructure network and assign flows of demand to it, bringing together

²⁴ <https://github.com/nismod/smif>

²⁵ Usher, W., & Russell, T. (2019). A software framework for the integration of infrastructure simulation models. *Journal of Open Research Software*, 7(1).

²⁶ Pant, R., Hall, J. W., & Blainey, S. P. (2016). Vulnerability assessment framework for interdependent critical infrastructures: case-study for Great Britain's rail network. *European Journal of Transportation and Infrastructure Research*, 16(1), 174-194.

²⁷ Pant, R., Thacker, S., Hall, J. W., Alderson, D., & Barr, S. (2018). Critical infrastructure impact assessment due to flood exposure. *Journal of Flood Risk Management*, 11(1), 22-33.

large amount of unique infrastructure data and assessing direct and indirect impacts of flooding at the basin level to the whole interconnected network. The paper is open-source, and reports equations and mathematical expressions to allow reproducibility of the process.

Thacker et al. (2017a)²⁸ similarly tried to represent the complex interactions and explore the relationships between the assets and networks of functionally dependent systems at different scales and proved it in England and Wales for the electricity and domestic flight network. They consequently developed a methodology for a systems-of-systems disruption analysis of Critical National Infrastructures (CNIs) through the algorithm that then became the one at the base of NISMOD's tools. The methodology included ways of mapping the spatial and topological characteristics of CNIs across scales, functional understanding of infrastructure dependencies, failure propagation and disruption calculation.

Thacker et al. (2017b)²⁹ as developed a national-scale databased and model of the energy, transport, water, waste, and digital communications sectors and tested 200,000 failure scenarios to identify infrastructure criticality hotspots. The resulting outcomes showed that hotspots were typically located around the periphery of urban areas where there were large facilities upon which many users depended or where several critical infrastructures were concentrated in one location.

Thacker et al (2018a)³⁰ developed a novel approach for the synthesis of multilevel electricity networks that preserved key structural and topological features to enable risk and resilience studies. The algorithm and equations to create the network with its nodes and edges at different hierarchical levels are reported. The topology of the network, source and sink nodes connected by edges at different voltage levels were created thanks to NISMOD tools. Adaptation options of the electricity system against hydrometeorological risks (such as a flood, wind-storm, or heat wave) were also evaluated with respect to a business-as-usual approach (Thacker et al., 2018b)³¹ for critical infrastructure network in the same geographical area. Mathematical explanation of the whole approach is given, to allow other similar analysis to be carried out in other Countries or regions. Adaptation measures were also evaluated with a cost benefit analysis. Results showed the large-magnitude impacts that could result from the failure of major electricity sub-stations in England and Wales, where adapting these substations through the installation of permanent flood protection

²⁸ Thacker, S., Pant, R., & Hall, J. W. (2017a). System-of-systems formulation and disruption analysis for multi-scale critical national infrastructures. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, 167, 30-41.

²⁹ Thacker, S., Barr, S., Pant, R., Hall, J. W., & Alderson, D. (2017b). Geographic hotspots of critical national infrastructure. *Risk Analysis*, 37(12), 2490-2505.

³⁰ Thacker, S., Hall, J. W., & Pant, R. (2018a). Preserving key topological and structural features in the synthesis of multilevel electricity networks for modeling of resilience and risk. *Journal of Infrastructure Systems*, 24(1), 04017043.

³¹ Thacker, S., Kelly, S., Pant, R., & Hall, J. W. (2018b). Evaluating the benefits of adaptation of critical infrastructures to hydrometeorological risks. *Risk Analysis*, 38(1), 134-150.

walls result the most effective solution to reduce hydrometeorological hazard risks when facing different future uncertainties.

Given its easy reproducibility, the toolkit was then expanded and applied to different countries and regions in the world, giving life to papers and reports about risk and resilience in many parts of the world.

The latest example is represented by Colombo et al. (2025)³², who used NISMOD tools open-gira and snkit at the African continental level. They developed the African Transport System Database (AfTS-Db), creating and standardizing asset and network data across all transport modes, including inter-modal connections, attributes of road and rail corridors and estimated annual statistics for airports and ports, in order to support a wider risk and resilience analysis for Africa at various levels. The dataset and codes to reproduce it are online and open-source (Colombo et al 2025³³, Pant et al 2025³⁴).

Reports

Pant et al. (2020)³⁵ produced an assessment for the UK National Infrastructure Commission (NIC), where NISMOD tools were used to pilot an approach to assess the key physical vulnerabilities of the current and future interdependent networks of energy, telecoms, transport and water. It drew out the vulnerabilities that arise from network architecture and how these were likely to change in the future, and informed the development of a framework to identify actions to assess, improve, and monitor the resilience of the system. The analysis allowed to show how interdependencies create disruptions to the network not only to the immediate neighbouring elements but also through a cascading effect, and how redundancy and backup supply for electricity can help reducing the failures. Due to NISMOD it was possible to create a first set of representations of future electricity networks, factoring in realistic future network scenarios of increased supply and demand and apply failure analysis to it.

NISMOD framework and respective tools were applied also to support international organizations, such as the World Bank, in analysing infrastructure risk and resilience in the countries part of the group. An example is represented by Pant et al. (2024)³⁶,

³² Colombo, S., Pant, R., Young, M., Thomas, F., Russell, T., Verschuur, J., & Hall, J. W. (2025). The African Transport Systems Database-a geospatial database of multi-modal connected networks. *Scientific Data*.

³³ Colombo, S., Pant, R., Young, M., Thomas, F., Russell, T., Verschuur, J., & Hall, J. W. (2025). The African Transport Systems Database - a geospatial database of multi-modal connected networks [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17861120>

³⁴ Pant, R., Colombo, S., Russell, T., & Thomas, F. (2025). nismod/Africa-transport-database: The African Transport Systems Database (AfTS-Db) (v1.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17609113>

³⁵ Pant, R., Russell, T., Zorn, C., Oughton, E. and Hall, J.W. (2020). Resilience study research for NIC - Systems analysis of interdependent network vulnerabilities. Environmental Change Institute, Oxford University, UK. Doi: <https://www.nic.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/Infrastructure-network-analysis.pdf>.

³⁶ Pant R., Peard, A., Thacker, S., Jaramillo, D., Russell, T., and Hall, J.W. (2024). Estimating investment needs for climate adaptation in the Eastern Caribbean. Final Report, Oxford Infrastructure Analytics Ltd.,

supporting the topic in the Country Climate Development Report (CCDR), Estimating investment needs for climate adaptation in Dominica, Grenada, St. Lucia, and St. Vincent and the Grenadines. It included a geospatial analysis to understand flood, storm and landslide exposures to infrastructure sectors including energy, transport, and water assets. The study found that much of the critical infrastructure in these countries is highly exposed to climate hazards such as storms, hurricanes, and landslides, and that because systems like ports and roads are limited and interconnected, disruptions can cascade through infrastructure and supply chains to cause significant economic losses. The study has, for the first time, estimated adaptation investment needs for national infrastructure systems using a spatially explicit, asset-scale, approach. The enhancement of resilience, through infrastructure adaptation, provides a means to address climate-related hazards and safeguard development progress that has taken decades to achieve. The effectiveness of chosen adaptation options was estimated by calculating the aggregated reduction in direct and indirect damages to the assets and services.

Oh et al. (2019)³⁷ World Bank final report “Addressing Climate Change In Transport - Pathway to Resilient Transport”, used the NISMOD tools to carry on a Transport Multi-Hazard Risk Analysis for Vietnam at the national and provincial scale, and to develop policy recommendation to enhance climate resilience of the transport sector. The scope of the national analysis covered key national-scale roads, railways, civil aviation, inland waterways, and maritime systems that make up Vietnam’s multimodal transportation infrastructure. At the national scale, the focus was to understand the economic impacts of disruptions to multimodal freight transportation due to infrastructure failures. Flooding and landslides under both current and future climate change conditions were intersected with transport infrastructure using a system-of-systems approach, demonstrating that exposure to extreme hazards was projected to increase substantially across all transport sectors in Vietnam under climate change scenarios. Furthermore, a systemic understanding of locations where infrastructure failures shows that climate change would generate escalating economic risks and provides a strong economic justification for investing in enhanced climate resilience across Vietnam’s transport networks.

Kesete et al (2021)³⁸ used the NISMOD toolkit to quantify the impact of climate change-induced flood risk on the transport network in Argentina, as a system-of-systems approach, where network models were developed to suitably represent the transport system as nodes and links. For each node and link, the study analysed

Oxford, UK. <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/099092624210521611/pdf/P179742-48fbbf63-5034-4b6c-adea-786c18e08131.pdf>

³⁷ Oh, J.E., Espinet Alegre, X., Pant, R., Koks, E.E., Russell, T., Schoenmakers, R. and Hall, J.W. (2019). Addressing Climate Change in Transport: Volume 2: Pathway to Resilient Transport. World Bank, Washington DC. Doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1596/32412>.

³⁸ Kesete, Y. Y., Raffo, V., Pant, R., Koks, E. E., Paltan, H., Russell, T., and Hall, J. W. (2021). Climate Change Risk Analysis of Argentina’s Land Transport Network. World Bank, Washington, DC. Doi: <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/36504>.

criticality, vulnerability, and risk, and provided adaptation strategies. The study found that major freight road and rail routes in Argentina are vulnerable to extreme flooding, with climate change expected to worsen disruptions. The resulting economic impacts could be substantial, depending on rerouting capacity and disruption duration. To address these risks, Argentina's National Roads Directorate (DNV) and Ministry of Transport (MoT) must integrate climate risk into long-term planning, account for broader macroeconomic losses, and strengthen internal capacity for transport risk assessment and resilient design.

Pant et al. (2022)³⁹, in their report for the UNDRR, summarized most of the preciously cited methodologies and frameworks to demonstrate that investment in energy, transport, water, telecoms, and waste infrastructure is essential for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals and the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction targets, yet growing climate risks threaten both existing and new assets, potentially reversing development gains. Climate-induced infrastructure failures can trigger cascading network effects across interconnected systems, highlighting the need to better understand and quantify systemic risks and adaptation costs. This contributing paper to the Global Assessment Report on Disaster Risk Reduction reviewed emerging technologies, methods, and case studies that used NISMOD tools to support climate risk assessment and adaptation planning at global, national, and local scales.

Conference proceedings

At UK level, recognizing the importance of critical infrastructure vulnerability in risk reduction planning, Pant et al. (2014)⁴⁰ developed a spatial risk assessment framework that quantifies infrastructure risk across multiple network failure configurations resulting from extreme hazard events, demonstrating its application through a national-scale case study of infrastructure network reliability, disruption, and overall risk. Similarly Pant et al. (2015)⁴¹ used NISMOD to analyse the systemic criticality of Britain's multi-modal transport networks. They used a multi-dimensional metric set, encompassing traffic flows, disruptions, rerouting capabilities, and multi-modal impacts, and demonstrated how to identify the key nodes and edges most

³⁹ Pant, R., Fuldauer, L.I., Hu, X., Koks, E., E., Paltan, H., Russell, T., Verschuur, J., Zorn, C. and Hall, J. W. (2022). From local to global scales – Quantifying climate risks and adaptation opportunities for networked infrastructure systems. United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR), Switzerland. Doi: www.undrr.org/quick/71687.

⁴⁰ Pant, R., Hall, J.W., Barr, S., and Alderson, D. (2014). Spatial Risk Analysis of Interdependent Infrastructure Networks Subjected to Extreme Hazards. *Vulnerability, Uncertainty and Risk*, pp. 677-686. Doi: <http://ascelibrary.org/doi/abs/10.1061/9780784413609.069>.

⁴¹ Pant, R., Hall, J.W., Blainey, S.P. and Preston, J.M. (2015). Assessing single point criticality of multi-modal transport networks at the national-scale. 25th European Safety and Reliability Conference, Switzerland. Available in CD-ROM.

critical to maintaining national mobility. While these abstracts are not openly accessible, both studies follow the NISMOD framework, which is thoroughly described across the wider literature reviewed here.

Ives et al. (2017)⁴² reported the analysis done on its infrastructure to provide in-depth assessments of the national infrastructure needs up in the long term (2050). The National Infrastructure Systems Model (NISMOD) was used to model different future transport (road and rail) and energy (electricity and heat) infrastructure demand and supply. The document is open and describes the process in detail. A number of other peer reviewed abstracts were produced using the NISMOD tools and methodology and presented in conferences and general assemblies such as European Geosciences Union (EGU) and American Geophysical Union (AGU) (Li et al. 2025⁴³ and 2024⁴⁴, respectively), presenting their flood risk analysis on road infrastructure in the UK, being able to assess direct damages as well as indirect rerouting issues due to floods.

Expanding the focus on the international horizon, for the Green Growth Knowledge Platform (GGKP) Annual Conference (Washington DC), Pant et al. (2017)⁴⁵ showed how they used NISMOD to create and analyse a system-of-systems framework of the Gaza Strip, demonstrating how electricity infrastructure failures generate cascading direct and indirect impacts across energy, water, wastewater, health, banking, and education systems, thereby supporting national-scale risk management and resilience planning in both developed and developing contexts.

In the proceedings of the DRI Technical Conference – Adaptive Pathways for Resilient Infrastructure (New Delhi, India), Pant et al. (2023)⁴⁶ presented a comprehensive assessment of systemic risks to transport networks due to current and future climate change driven river and coastal flooding hazards. Thanks to the NISMOD tools, through a detailed transport network climate risk and adaptation

⁴² Ives, M. C., Usher, W., Hall, J. W., Silberman, A., Letti, B., Large, J., ... & Robson, C. (2017). Modelling future scenarios of infrastructure demand for the UK's National Infrastructure Assessment. In *International Symposia for Next Generation Infrastructure*. Newcastle University.

⁴³ Li, Y., Pant, R., Russell, T., Thomas, F., Hall, J., & Oldham, P. (2025, April). A Process-based Flow Model for Assessing Direct and Indirect Damages to Flooded Roads in Great Britain. In EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts (pp. EGU25-9365).

⁴⁴ Li, Y., Pant, R., Russell, T., Thomas, F., Hall, J. W., & Oldham, P. (2024). Enhancing Resilience of the UK Roads Network: An Integrated Process-based Flow and Stress-testing Model for Flood-Induced Disruption Assessment. AGU24.

⁴⁵ Pant, R., Thacker, S., and Hall, J. (2017). System-of-systems Framework for Global Infrastructure Vulnerability Assessments. Green Growth Knowledge Platform (GGKP) Annual Conference, Washington DC, US. Doi: <https://www.greengrowthknowledge.org/research/system-systems-framework-global-infrastructure-vulnerability-assessments>.

⁴⁶ Pant, R., Jaramillo, D., & Hall, J.W. (2023). Systemic assessment of climate risks and adaptation options for transport networks in East Africa. In Coalition for Disaster Resilient Infrastructure (CDRI) 2022 Conference Proceedings, Sustainable and Resilient Infrastructure, 8:sup2, 1-143. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23789689.2023.2181552>

assessment, this study delivered an analytical methodology and decision-support tool to prioritize adaptation investments, enabling transport planners and stakeholders in Kenya, Tanzania, Uganda, and Zambia to better understand climate risks, evaluate costs and benefits, and align resilience strategies with long-term planning objectives. Since the methodology and tools are clearly depicted and free to use, the reproducibility of the same analysis in other countries and regions was ensured.

The Jamaica Systemic Risk Assessment Tool (J-SRAT) was presented at the 2025 EGU General Assembly, showing how to address the challenges represented by extreme floods and storms in Caribbean islands such as Jamaica and demonstrating how systemic spatial risk assessment is needed to map locations of vulnerable infrastructure assets and quantify their socio-economic impacts. With NISMOD tools Pant et al. (2025)⁴⁷ have assembled multi-hazard climate datasets, developed spatial network flow models of interdependent energy and transport systems, identified infrastructure vulnerability hotspots, estimated direct damages and indirect economic losses, and designed and optimized resilience interventions by comparing their systemic costs and benefits to support long-term climate adaptation investment decisions. J-SRAT was used as a decision-support platform for the Government of Jamaica and other stakeholders to evaluate and prioritize policies to reduce climate risks and strengthen infrastructure resilience, with ongoing advancements extending its application across Jamaica and the wider Caribbean islands. The platform and paper are not open-access, but the codes to reproduce the analysis are open, and the source code for the visualisation platform is open too.

Book chapters

Two open-access book chapters are included here, both written to demonstrate the effectiveness and practical utility of the NISMOD toolkit.

Pant et al. (2016)⁴⁸, thanks to the NISMOD toolkit, highlighted the severe but less frequent risk of infrastructure systems facing disruptions that can halt service provision. Due to the interconnected nature of these systems, failures can cascade, causing widespread societal and economic impacts. Their methodology quantified these risks in economic terms, providing a basis for advocating investment in infrastructure resilience. This chapter presented a risk assessment approach

⁴⁷ Pant, R., Thomas, F., Russell, T., Campbell, J., Taylor, A., Samuels, R., & Hall, J. (2025). *Building Systemic Risk Assessment Tools for Climate Adaptation Assessment in the Caribbean—Case Study for Jamaica* (No. EGU25-20176). Copernicus Meetings.

⁴⁸ Pant, R., Thacker, S., Hall, J.W., Barr, S., Alderson, D. and Kelly, S. (2016). Analysing the risks of failure of interdependent infrastructure networks. In: Hall, J.W., Tran, M., Hickford, A.J. and Nicholls, R.J. (eds) *The Future of National Infrastructure: A System-of-Systems Approach*, p.241.

focused on the potential for failures in interdependent infrastructures and the resulting negative economic and social consequences.

Pant (2022)⁴⁹ presented data-driven models and tools leveraging NISMOD to evaluate the costs and benefits of climate adaptation for infrastructure networks across multiple spatial scales. The framework integrates assessments of hazards, vulnerabilities, risks, and resilience options, accounting for both direct impacts and cascading network effects. Case studies across Tanzania, Vietnam, and Argentina illustrate how the framework estimates climate hazard risks to critical transport links, with the authors emphasising that effective adaptation demands cross-sectoral collaboration and the embedding of adaptation strategies into infrastructure planning, underpinned by advanced data analytics.

Conclusions

The literature reviewed here offers an account of the origins and evolution of NISMOD tools and analysis, underscoring their significance in both short- and long-term infrastructure risk and resilience analysis. The breadth of publications, combined with open-access availability, well-documented frameworks, open-source code, and clear documentation, ensures that NISMOD can be applied across diverse contexts worldwide, equipping decision-makers, researchers, and stakeholders with the tools needed to plan and build resilient infrastructure systems.

⁴⁹ Pant R. (2022). Advances in Climate Adaptation Modeling of Infrastructure Networks. In: Kondrup C. et al. (eds) Climate Adaptation Modelling. Springer Climate. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-86211-4_19.